

Synthesis of 2-Chloro-4-(*p*-methoxyphenylureido)-6-(3'-arylazo-4'-hydroxy-1'-naphthyl)-*s*-triazines

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Reactive dyes as a group have made it possible to achieve a wide variety of fast, bright shade in dyeing and printing¹. Chang synthesised halogenated triazine azo dyes for cellulose by Friedl's craft method². Reactive azo dyes were prepared by ICI³ from 1-naphthol, cyanuric chloride and diazotised metanilic acid. Naik and Desai⁴ synthesised reactive dyes containing triazine ring system. With a view to synthesise more reactive dyes, we have synthesised 2-chloro-4-(*p*-methoxyphenylureido)-6-(3'-arylazo-4'-hydroxy-1'-naphthyl)-*s*-triazine derivatives using 1-naphthol, cyanuric chloride, *p*-methoxyphenylurea and various diazotising components (R).

Experimental

2,4-Dichloro-6-(4'-hydroxy-1'-naphthyl)-*s*-triazine : To a mixture of 1-naphthol (4.32 g, 0.03 mol) and cyanuric chloride (5.52 g, 0.03 mol) dissolved in dry benzene at 5–10°, was added AlCl₃ (6.0 g) during 2 h at 5–10° and the mixture was stirred for 4 h. The temperature was then raised to 25–30° and kept overnight. The product was then filtered and decomposed in HCl and ice-cold water and the resulting solid was dried (76%), m.p. 224°.

2-Chloro-4-(*p*-methoxyphenylureido)-6-(4'-hy-

droxy-1'-naphthyl)-*s*-triazine : A mixture of *p*-methoxyphenylurea (3.32 g, 0.02 mol) and 2,4-dichloro-6-(4'-hydroxy-1'-naphthyl)-*s*-triazine (5.84 g, 0.02 mol) was dissolved in acetone and heated at 90° for 3 h at pH 6.5–7.0. The mixture was then cooled to room temperature and poured on ice and the resulting solid was dried (70%), m.p. 242°.

Coupling of diazo solution with 2-chloro-4-(*p*-methoxyphenylureido)-6-(4'-hydroxy-1'-naphthyl)-*s*-triazine : H-acid (3.19 g, 0.01 mol) was diazotised in the usual manner. The resulting diazonium solution was then added into a well-cooled stirred mixture of 2-chloro-4-(*p*-methoxyphenylureido)-6-(4'-hydroxy-1'-naphthyl)-*s*-triazine (4.21 g, 0.01 mol) and acetone (40 ml). The reaction mass was then stirred at 0–5° for 3 h, maintaining pH 8. Sodium chloride (10% w/v) solution was then added with stirring until the solid material was precipitated. It was filtered, washed with small amount of sodium chloride solution and purified from DMF-acetone (65–80%), m.p. 219–312°. Physical data of dyes D₁–D₁₂ (68–80% yields) are given in Table 1.

Application : The dye bath for viscose and silk contained the following : viscose rayon/silk cloth (2 g), dye solution (40 ml; 0.1 % w/v), salt solution (8 ml; 30% w/v) and sodium carbonate solution (8 ml; 10% w/v) keeping material-to-liquor ratio 1 : 40 and total volume of solution in dye-bath 80 ml. In the dyeing process the pre-treated pattern (2 g) was introduced in the dye-bath containing dye solution (40 ml, 0.1% w/v) and distilled water (24 ml). The contents were frequently stirred over a period of 15 min at 50°. Salt solution (4 ml) was then added and the temperature raised to 80° in 20 min. the additional salt solution (4 ml) was added and stirring continued for 20 min. The

TABLE 1 – PHYSICAL AND EXHAUSTION DATA OF DYES D₁–D₁₂*

Dye no.	R	M.p. °C	Shade of dyeing on fibers	λ_{\max}^{**}	R_f	% Exhaustion		
						Viscose	Silk	Wool
D ₁	H-Acid	269	Violet	505	0.76	72.5	65.0	53.0
D ₂	J-Acid	302	Maroon-red	530	0.89	77.0	68.5	62.0
D ₃	Gamma acid	280	Violet	560	0.85	70.0	63.0	59.5
D ₄	Tobias acid	237	Light orange	540	0.76	69.0	54.5	56.0
D ₅	Sulphotobias acid	265	Orange	545	0.70	69.5	58.0	52.0
D ₆	Metanilic acid	244	Pink	485	0.80	72.0	63.0	62.0
D ₇	5-Sulphoanthranilic acid	289	Red	515	0.78	69.5	57.0	55.0
D ₈	1,2,4-Acid	310	Brown	405	0.81	68.0	62.0	53.0
D ₉	Chicago acid	219	Yellowish	510	0.74	72.0	68.5	63.5
D ₁₀	<i>p</i> -Aminoacetanilide-3-sulphonic acid	300	Pink	495	0.78	71.0	63.0	55.0
D ₁₁	Peri acid	312	Orange	490	0.81	74.0	70.5	59.0
D ₁₂	Sulphanilic acid	289	Orange (Red)	520	0.72	71.5	69.0	62.5

*Satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

**Dye concn. 2×10^{-3} M in water at 28° (Bauch and Lamb Spectronic 20 spectrophotometer).

pattern was lifted up from the dye-bath, sodium carbonate solution (4 ml) then added to the dye-bath and the pattern was reintroduced. The dyeing was continued with agitation for 1 h at 80°. The pattern was then washed several times with cold water and finally with Lissapol D (ICI; 0.1 g) in water (50 ml) and boiled for 15 min. The pattern was washed with hot water and dried.

The dye-bath for wool continued the following : wool fibre (2 g), dye solution (40 ml; 0.1% w/v) and Nevadine AN (20 mg) keeping material-to-liquor ratio 1 : 30 and total volume of dye-bath 60 ml. The pre-treated fibres (2 g) was introduced in the dye-bath, adjusted to pH 3 and stirred frequently at 50°. The temperature was then raised to 90° in a period of 30 min. The dyeing was continued for further 45 min. Towards the end of dyeing, pH of the bath was neutralised by addition of ammonia and the dyeing continued for further 15 min.

The results on fastness properties show that the light fastness ranges from moderate to good for all the fibres. Wash fastness is good to excellent for all the fibres. Dyes when applied on fibres gave violet to brown shades with good to excellent exhaustion (Table 1).

2-Chloro-4-(*p*-methoxyphenylureido)-6-(4'-hydroxy-1'-naphthyl)-*s*-triazine were separated on tlc using solvent system benzyl alcohol + DMF + water (30 : 20 : 20) : ν_{\max} 1 445–1 475 (N=N), 780–815 (C₃N₃), 1 560–1 590 (NH), 1 645–1 655 (C=O) and 700–740 cm⁻¹ (C-Cl); λ_{\max} in Table 1.

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